

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES AND SEPARATION OF ISOMERS

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Bromo (5 and 7)-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinolines have been synthesised and the isomers separated.

Recently substituted 4-aminoquinoline derivatives in a large number, containing substituents in different positions, have been reported by various investigators (Surrey and Hammer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 113; Hauser *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1946, 68, 1232; Reed *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1946, 68, 1239; Von Ardenne and Shoule, *ibid.*, 1944, 66, 1285; Price and Roberts, *ibid.*, 1946, 68, 1204; Magidson and Roleston, *J. Gen. Chem. Phys.*, USSR, 1937, 7, 1896). Some of these quinoline derivatives have been reported to possess antimalarial properties (Steck *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 129).

With the idea that the introduction of the bromine atom and the methoxy group might enhance the activity and permeability of the drug, the synthesis of the following type of compounds was undertaken.

3-Bromo-4-methoxyaniline was condensed with ethyl oxalacetate in glacial acetic acid. The condensed product was cyclised by pouring it into liquid paraffin, heated to 260°. The solid separating on cooling was found to be a mixture of two isomers, 5-bromo- and 7-bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylates.

When *m*-substituted aniline is used in the reaction as a starting material, two isomers are possible. The isomers have high melting points. A mixture of this type can be separated by fractional crystallisation. 7-Isomer is less soluble and melts at a higher temperature (Surrey and Hammer, *loc. cit.*). These authors carried out the separation of isomers generally at the ester stage, but in certain cases this method did not work successfully.

The 7- and 5-bromo isomers have been separated by crystallisation from acetic acid and conform to the observations of Surrey and Hammer (*loc. cit.*) as regards solubility and m.p.

The first isomer on hydrolysis with sodium hydroxide solution furnishes 7-bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylic acid, which on decarboxylation yields 7-bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline.

The second isomer (5-bromo-) on hydrolysis by alkali yields 5-bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylic acid. The quantity of this quinoline acid, thus obtained, was very small. Further investigation is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 5- or 7-bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylate was prepared by heating a mixture of ethyl oxalacetate (14 g.), 3-bromo-4-methoxyaniline (25 g.) and glacial acetic acid (60 c.c.) at 50-60° for 4 hours. The reaction mixture after keeping overnight was poured into

ice-water. It was neutralised with 35% NaOH solution. The ether extract of the product after washing alternately with HCl (0.5 N) and NaOH (0.5 N) was dried over potassium carbonate. After removal of the ether, the residual oil (18 g.) was added to liquid paraffin at 250°. The separated solid was filtered and washed with petrol. The crude product showed a wide range of melting point.

Separation of Isomers.—The above mentioned product was crystallised from five times its weight of hot acetic acid. 7-Bromo isomer first crystallised out as small yellow needles, m.p. 278° (decomp.). (Found : Br, 24.73. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4NBr$ requires Br, 24.54%). The filtrate was diluted with water, when impure 5-bromo isomer was obtained. After repeated crystallisations from acetic acid and ethanol, the pure ester was obtained, m.p. 222°. (Found : Br, 24.84. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4NBr$ requires Br, 24.54%).

7-Bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the corresponding ester. It crystallised from acetic acid in small yellow needles, m.p. 283° (decomp.). (Found : Br, 26.98. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4NBr$ requires Br, 26.85%).

7-Bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline was obtained when the 7-bromo acid was decarboxylated by heating it in liquid paraffin. It crystallised from boiling ethanol as a white granular solid, m.p. 260°. (Found : Br, 31.80. $C_{10}H_8O_2NBr$ requires Br, 31.50%).

5-Bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline-2-carboxylic acid was prepared by hydrolysing the 5-bromo ester as before. It crystallised from acetic acid in small needles, m.p. 216°.

7-Bromo-6-methoxy-4-chloroquinoline was prepared in the usual manner by heating 7-bromo-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline (6 g.) with $POCl_3$ (24 c.c.) for 2 hours. The 4-chloro derivative crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 200°.

Attempt to prepare 7-bromo-6-methoxy-4-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutyl)-aminoquinoline diphosphate was made by refluxing the mixture of 7-bromo-6-methoxy-4-chloroquinoline (4.1 g.) and 4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamine (6.4 g.) for 7 hours at 160-80°. The hot reaction mixture was passed into 30 c.c. of 50% acetic acid solution. It was then neutralised with a strong solution of NaOH. The ether extract of the alkaline mixture was dried, and on removal of ether a thick oil separated, which was converted into its diphosphate by treatment with phosphoric acid. All attempts to crystallise this compound failed. The melting point range was between 210° and 215°.

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